

The BioData Ecosystem: ELIXIR and the NIH Office of Data Science Strategy at ISMB 2023

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Summary

ELIXIR Europe and the National Institutes of Health Office of Data Science Strategy joined forces at the 2023 ISMB/ECCB meeting to understand the challenges and strengths of the Global BioData Ecosystem from those who create, manage and run those resources.

Background

In the current era of data-driven research and innovation, the availability and utilisation of diverse databases plays a pivotal role in advancing scientific knowledge and creating societal impact. Large, complex datasets are fueling new discoveries and driving innovation, but these valuable resources require robust infrastructure and collaboration to reach their full potential. At the 2023 Intelligent Systems for Molecular Biology (ISMB) meeting held jointly with the European Conference on Computational Biology (ECCB) in Lyon, France, ELIXIR Europe and the National Institutes of Health Office of Data Science Strategy (NIH ODSS) co-organized a track focussing on the BioData Ecosystem, its sustainability and interconnectedness.

ELIXIR is a life science data research infrastructure. As an intergovernmental treaty organisation, it is made up of 24 Node countries across Europe and the European Molecular Biology Laboratory, representing hundreds of research institutions and thousands of individual life science researchers. The National Institutes of Health's Office of Data Science Strategy is a central office that coordinates data science strategy, policy and resource activities across the broader US NIH. Individually and together ELIXIR and the NIH ODSS lead the way in enabling and supporting the development of the biological data resources that form a sustainable, interconnected biodata ecosystem propelling life science research globally.

This report details the three sessions that explored best practices for developing and utilising biological data resources. By bringing together resource representatives, consortium leads, and life science data experts, the track fostered discussion on strategies, challenges, and successes in leveraging data for scientific advancement and societal impact. The panellists shared and discussed strategies, challenges, and successes for leveraging data to drive discovery and transformative outcomes.

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2. Office of Data Science Strategy, National Institutes of Health, Bethesda, Maryland, 20892, United States

Session one - Core Resources at the Heart of Life Sciences

Empowering Discoveries and Insights

Moderator: Peter Maccallum

Speaker	Presentation
Juan Antonio Vizcaino <i>EMBL European Bioinformatics Institute, United Kingdom</i>	PRIDE & ProteomeXchange: Making proteomics data FAIR
Tom Pollard <i>Massachusetts Institute of Technology (MIT), United States</i>	PhysioNet: A Quarter Century of Open Health Data
Ugis Sarkans <i>EMBL European Bioinformatics Institute, United Kingdom</i>	From ArrayExpress to BioStudies
Josephine Burgin <i>EMBL European Bioinformatics Institute, United Kingdom</i>	The European Nucleotide Archive
Alex Bateman <i>EMBL European Bioinformatics Institute, United Kingdom</i>	InterPro: Bringing together protein families resources for sustainability
Nicola Bordin <i>University College London, United Kingdom</i>	CATH: Protein Structure Classification Database
Jan Gerken <i>Leibniz Institute DSMZ - German Collection of Microorganisms and Cell Cultures GmbH, Germany</i>	BRENDA: 35 Years of Empowering Enzymology and Beyond

This session highlighted the critical role of core resources in life sciences research, facilitating data sharing, analysis, and knowledge generation. A key theme emerged around the importance of pushing open data models and formats, so that users can align with databases before data collection begins, thus streamlining deposition and making reanalysis for new scientific questions easier. The European Nucleotide Archive highlighted the usefulness of brokers here, as its data broker network connects researchers with the most relevant databases in a way that is scalable. Designations like *ELIXIR Core Data Resource* also offer valuable signposting for researchers seeking the best place to deposit their data or the highest quality data for reuse. These mechanisms are becoming increasingly important as the requirements for sensitive data handling grow, as PRIDE demonstrated through the possibility of reidentifying human subjects from proteomics data. PRIDE and ProteomeXchange showcased the impact of standardisation of open data, with one resource boasting over 1.12 petabytes of data downloaded and fueling over 600 publications. However, PhysioNet reminded us that "garbage in equals garbage out", which is especially important in recent years, as good machine learning models rely heavily on high-quality, diverse datasets. Databases that prioritise quality over quantity and encompass a variety of data types will better empower researchers and lead to more reliable results.

Finally, there was recognition that all data resources have a finite life cycle. The creation and membership of a consortium was one solution for sustainability, at least for the data, with a tendency to cluster individual data resources into networked knowledge bases. An alternative is for older services to be retired but their content retained as part of more advanced successors. Indeed, the interdependent consortium structure mapped out by InterPro has prevented loss of long-term data from now defunct resources. Such retirement can even benefit research, as the transition of ArrayExpress from a microarray-specific platform to the more generic BioStudies platform should allow better integration of diverse and emerging data types, including imaging data. Environmental sustainability was also addressed, as InterPro raised the advantages of implementing efficient coding and deployment practices, which has significantly reduced their carbon footprint. As for financial stability, the value of being identified as an [ELIXIR Core Data Resource](#) or [Global Core Biodata Resource](#) has been recognised in national funding applications.

Session two - The Federated/Distributed Landscape: Unleashing the Potential of Collaborative Data Sharing

Moderator: Ishwar Chandramouliswaran

Speaker	Presentation
Heidi Imker <i>University of Illinois at Urbana-Champaign, United States</i>	A Landscape Analysis of Biodata Resources
Mallory Freeberg, <i>EMBL European Bioinformatics Institute, United Kingdom</i>	[Federated] EGA: Providing global discovery and access for sensitive human data
Ana Van Gulick <i>Figshare, United States</i>	The Coopetition model of collaboration in the NIH Generalist Repository Ecosystem Initiative
Obi Griffith, <i>Washington University, United States</i>	CIViC: Accelerating the expert-crowdsourcing of cancer variant interpretation
Laura Hughes, <i>Scripps Research, United States</i>	NIAID Data Ecosystem Discovery Portal: creating a federated search engine to discover infectious and immune-mediated disease data

This session highlighted the challenges and opportunities surrounding data sharing in a federated/distributed landscape, exploring the potential and impact of collaborative approaches to data integration and analysis. Representatives from key resources, including a landscape analysis, came together to showcase their initiatives, strategies, and innovations in advancing the federated/distributed landscape.

Heidi Imker introduced the topic with a comprehensive text-mining analysis of scientific literature, which identified data resources with funders from across the globe. A key takeaway was the overwhelming fragmentation of these data resources, as evidenced by the presence of 3,112 separate databases. This lack of discoverability and standardisation hinders research progress. However, several presentations offered promising solutions. The "Federated European Genome Phenome Archive" demonstrated the effectiveness of a federated model with defined data access protocols and policies for sensitive data. The "Coopetition Concept" presented by the Generalist Repositories provided a framework for cooperation in certain areas (FAIR principles, best practices) while allowing healthy competition between repositories in others (data types, visualisation). The CIViC database exemplified best practices in data interpretation and community management and illustrated the importance of curators. The NIAID ecosystem is addressing the search and discovery challenge through metadata aggregation and translation tools. These successful approaches were all presented as ways of working together on global priorities from pandemics to population genomics and pave the way for a more collaborative and efficient data sharing landscape in the future.

Session three - Knowledge and Impact from Data: Harnessing the Power of Diverse Databases

Moderator: Fabio Liberante

Speaker	Presentation
Alan Bridge <i>SIB Swiss Institute of Bioinformatics, Switzerland</i>	UniProtKB – a hub for protein knowledge
Melissa Haendel <i>University of North Carolina at Chapel Hill, United States</i>	National COVID Cohort Collaborative (N3C)
Jing Chen <i>University of California San Diego, United States</i>	The Network Data Exchange (NDEX)
Henning Hermjakob <i>EMBL European Bioinformatics Institute, United Kingdom</i>	Connecting Molecules and Organisations - IMEx Molecular Interactions and Reactome Pathways
Ana Rath <i>Inserm, France</i>	Orphadata Science: a global core data resource for rare disease knowledge
Damian Szklarczyk <i>SIB Swiss Institute of Bioinformatics, Switzerland</i>	The STRING Database: A Comprehensive Functional Annotation of Non-Model Organism Proteomes
Melissa Harrison <i>EMBL European Bioinformatics Institute, United Kingdom</i>	Europe PMC - connecting the literature to data

This session showcased the vast potential of diverse databases and the knowledge that can be unlocked through collaboration and interconnection. It looked at the ways data can be networked and integrated from multiple sources to provide advanced, higher level knowledge collections with greater impact. The session brought together representatives from a collection of prominent databases to share their insights, contributions, and strategies for leveraging data to drive discovery and transformative outcomes. UniProt exemplified this by combining human curation, computational analysis, and data from external sources (ChEBI, Rhea) to create a comprehensive protein annotation resource. Their success is evident in the very high web traffic, demonstrating strong community adoption.

Themes picked up in the session included the added value and sustainability of consortia (IMEx, N3C, UniProt), the development of curator recognition and credit systems and of common toolkits and standards for biocuration (IMEx, Europe PMC) and the unique collections of linked data which can be built for specialist communities (STRING, Orphadata). The session also demonstrated the value of literature as an indicator of impact (N3C, Europe PMC) and some of the tools available to all resource providers to evaluate this for themselves (Europe PMC). The importance of data diversity was further emphasised by IMEx and Orphadata. IMEx highlighted the power of collaboration, with 12 international partners contributing data and expertise to establish common file formats, curation guidelines, and confidence scores. Orphadata, a resource dedicated to rare disease research, aggregates data sets, applications, studies, and analysis tools, fostering interoperability and facilitating connections to other databases. These presentations underscored the value of leveraging diverse data sources and perspectives to create richer, more informative resources.

Conclusion

The three sessions brought together users, providers and funders of databases, focused on data-centric research - connecting best practices, shared challenges, and spawning new ideas for future approaches among the resource providers.

The joint ELIXIR and NIH ODSS session on biological data resources showcased the impressive progress made in building a sustainable and interconnected biodata ecosystem. Key themes emerged throughout the sessions, highlighting the importance of:

- **Core data resources:** These well-established resources act as the foundation for life science research, facilitating data sharing and knowledge generation. Their ongoing sustainment and collaboration are crucial.
- **Federated/distributed data sharing:** Collaborative approaches to data integration and analysis unlock the full potential of the vast data landscape. Standards, trust, and shared technology are key to successful federations.
- **Data as a research output:** Recognising the value of data curation and crediting curators is essential for maintaining high-quality databases.
- **Knowledge generation and impact:** Integrating data from diverse sources empowers researchers to create advanced knowledge collections with greater societal impact.

The conference track fostered a spirit of collaboration and highlighted the critical role of data resources in driving scientific discovery. Moving forward, continued investment in infrastructure, fostering collaboration, and recognising data as a scientific contribution will be crucial for realising the full potential of the biodata ecosystem.

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